

EUROPEAN MIDDLEWARE INITIATIVE

GLITE GSS & GSOAP PLUGIN LIBRARIES – FUNCTIONAL DESCRIPTION

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1 INTRODUCTION

Both security-oriented modules discussed in this Functional Description are internal libraries used exclusively within other EMI products.

2 GSS

The GSS module (`glite-lbjp-common-gss`) provides GSS functions (GSS-API¹ and several non-GSS Globus calls) wrapped to a secure network communication library with strict timing control (via timeout arguments) of all remote operations.

3 GSOAP PLUGIN

The GSS plugin for gSoap (`glite-lbjp-common-gsoap-plugin`) provides secured communication via GSS, as well as strict timing control of all operations through `glite-lbjp-common-gss`.

¹<http://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc2744>